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Tourism Industry in Tamilnadu- A Strategy for a Steady Growth

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INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the major components of India's services and engines of growth, contributing around 6.11 percent of GDP and 10 percent of employment. This sector is estimated to create 78 jobs per million Indian rupees of investment compared to 45 jobs per million rupees in the manufacturing sector (Planning Commission, 2011). The annual growth of this sector is estimated to be 8.1 percent during the last five years. India has become a preferred tourist destination globally. Tamil Nadu is among the premier states in terms of tourist destination within and outside the country.

Indian Tourism Industry- An overview

Travel & Tourism generated, either directly or indirectly, 7.6% of employment in India in 2013. This industry provides heritage, cultural, medical, business and sports tourism. The Indian tourism sector has been flourishing in recent years due to improved connectivity to and from the country. Also, a better lodging facility at the tourist destinations has been a factor which has contributed to increase Foreign Tourists Arrival (FTA). The Policies and changes implemented by the Government of India has also been instrumental in providing the necessary boost to the Indian tourism and hospitality industry and attracting more and more foreign tourists every year. Number of Domestic Tourist Visits (DTV's) to all states and Union Territories in India from 2000- 2013 are shown in Table. Visitor's percentage fluctuates from time to time, but in the last few years it grows steadily.

Table 1: Number of Domestic Tourist Visits (DTVs) to all States/UTs in India, 2000-2013

Year	No. of Domestic Tourist Visits to States/UTs (in Million)	Percentage change over the previous year
2000	220.11	15.4
2001	236.47	7.4
2002	269.60	14.0
2003	309.04	14.6
2004	366.27	18.5
2005	392.01	7.0
2006	462.32	17.9
2007	526.56	13.9
2008	563.03	6.9
2009	668.80	18.8
2010	747.70	11.8
2011	864.53	15.6
2012 \$	1045.05	20.9
2013 (P)	1145.28	9.6

Source: State/ Union Territory Tourism Departments.
(P): Provisional, \$-DTV figure of 2012 has been revised

Tamilnadu Tourism - An Overview

Tamil Nadu was ranked Second in India in the domestic tourist arrivals next to Andhra Pradesh and also Second in foreign tourist arrivals next to Maharashtra in 2012. In 2013, Tamil Nadu stands first in India

in domestic tourist arrivals for the first time and a close second in foreign tourist arrivals. Tamil Nadu has in recent times become one of the leading destinations for Medical Tourism and Wellness Tourism. The Tourists visiting Tamil Nadu are mostly coming from USA, Australia, New Zealand, Belgium, France, Germany, Israel, Italy, Switzerland, Netherlands, UK, Spain, Scandinavia, Russia, Malaysia etc. And tourism attractions in Tamilnadu are Heritage Attractions, Pilgrim Centres, Beaches, Rural Tourism, Hill Stations, Wildlife Sanctuaries, Adventure Tourism, and Health Tourism. Mega tourist destinations in Tamilnadu are Mahabalipuram, Pilgrimage Heritage, Madurai – Rameshwaram – Kanyakumari, Thanjavur.

Table 2: Growth of Tourism Industry from 2011-2013

Tamil Nadu Tourism – Growth Statistics Year	Domestic Tourists (in Lakhs)	Foreign Tourists (in Lakhs)	Total (in Lakhs)
2011	1367.51	33.08	1400.59
2012	1841.37	35.62	1876.99
2013	2442.32	39.90	2482.22

Source: State/ UT Tourism Departments. (P): Provisional.

Government of Tamilnadu Tourism Policy (1992)

A Tourism Policy was first announced by the Government of Tamilnadu during 1992. The salient features of the policy were:

- Area development approach, keeping foreign tourists in mind
- Encouraging private sector investments in tourism
- Promotion of local and domestic tourism
- Manpower development in the hotel and tourism sector
- Adequate publicity for tourism promotions in India and abroad
- Promotion of culture through tourism fairs and festivals
- Developing facilities for tented tourism, adventure tourism and beach tourism
- Using a growth centre approach and integrating tourism development with the overall development of the place and its people.

Table 3: Shares of Top 10 States and UTs of India in Number of Domestic Tourist Visits in 2013

S. No	State/UT	Domestic Tourist Visit in 2013 (P)	
		Number	Percentage Share
1.	Tamil Nadu	244232487	21.3
2.	Uttar Pradesh	226531091	19.8
3.	Andhra Pradesh	152102150	13.3
4.	Karnataka	98010140	8.6
5.	Maharashtra	82700556	7.2
6.	Madhya Pradesh	63110709	5.5
7.	Rajasthan	30298150	2.6
8.	Gujarat	27412517	2.4
9.	West Bengal	25547300	2.2
10.	Chhattisgarh	22801031	2.0
Total of Top 10 States		972746131	84.9
Others		172534312	15.1
G.Total		1145280443	100.0

Source: State/ UT Tourism Departments. (P): Provisional.

The table and diagram shows share of top ten states and union territories of India received total number of domestic tourists in the year 2013. Among the top ten states, Tamilnadu received 21.3 percent of total domestic tourists followed by Utterpradesh at 19.8 percent, Andhrapradesh received 13.3 percent and

minimum number of domestic tourist are in Chhattisgarh at 2.0 percent. The reason for Tamilnadu receiving more domestic tourists are, due to the government participation in promoting tourism sector.

Source: State/ UT Tourism Departments. (P): Provisional.

Government of Tamilnadu Tourism Development Approach for 2014-2015

- To declare '**Clean and Green Zones**' around tourist attractions by the local bodies
- To create and develop **integrated tourism circuits** based on our unique civilization, heritage and culture in partnership with States, private sector and other agencies
- To develop Tamil Nadu as an "**All Seasons, All Budget Tourist Destination**"
- To showcase **Wellness Tourism** potential
- To make **Tourism as everybody's business**, so as to have people's participation
- Conducting **Marketing Meets** with tour operators, travel agents at important Countries, which are contributing to tourist arrivals to our State
- To project the uniqueness and inimitable nature of our cultural heritage
- To analyse tourist behaviour and their needs to evolve packages for each of the target markets.
- Special '**Home Coming**' packages for **ethnic Indian population** in Mauritius, Malaysia and other Countries
- **Adventure Tourism and Beach Tourism** to be promoted in a big way through experts.
- Art, Culture and Crafts are to be promoted under **Cultural Tourism**
- **Promotion of MICE Tourism** – Tamil Nadu has excellent facilities for Conferences and Exhibitions. **MICE Tourism** (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions) will be promoted to attract large segments of Businessmen, Industrialists, Investors, Specialists, Artists etc. to make Tamil Nadu as a hub for their national and international activities.
- **Human Resources Development** - For enhancing the quality of tourist services, **Capacity Building Training** will be conducted for the stake holders, utilizing the expertise in the industry and catering institutes.
- **Digital / Electronic Media for Tourism Publicity** - Wide publicity will be given through print and electronic media for attracting large number of tourists to our State.

Tamilnadu Tourism Development Corporation Limited

TTDC was incorporated on 30.6.1971 with the objective of providing infrastructure in all the major Tourist destinations in the State. TTDC has made rapid strides over the years and it has now a chain of 55 Hotels and a fleet of 17 Coaches. It has also established Youth Hostels at the Hill Resorts of Ooty, Kodaikanal and Yercaud catering to budget Tourists. Some of the Hotels were given on lease in the past and the rest managed by the Corporation.

Hotels Division

Twelve TTDC Hotels have already been upgraded during the past three years. Efforts are being taken to upgrade the remaining Hotels on a demand basis with the help of Professional Architects

E-Governance Initiatives of TTDC

TTDC has earned the distinction of being the first State Tourism Corporation to introduce on-line booking of Tours and Hotels. This has helped TTDC to improve its revenue significantly through online bookings of Tours and Hotels. This has helped TTDC to improve its revenue significantly through online bookings of Tours and Hotels. Mobile reservation of TTDC Hotels and Tours was also launched on the World Tourism Day i.e. 27th September 2012. This has helped the Tourists to book TTDC Hotels and Tours through all the Mobile Networks.

The revenue generated through On-line bookings has registered quantum leap at 45% during the year 2013-14 with earnings of Rs.776 lakhs compared to the earnings of Rs.535 lakhs during the year 2012-13. Wi-Fi connectivity has been provided at five major TTDC Hotels at Mamallapuram, Ooty, Kodaikanal, Coimbatore and Madurai Unit II. This will be extended to other TTDC Hotels in a phased manner based on the response from Tourists.

Financial Performance

The financial performance of TTDC has been very good during the past three years as detailed below

Table 4: Financial performance of TTDC from 2008-09 to 2013-2014

Year	Turnover (Rupees in Crores)	Net Profit (Rupees in Crores)
2008-09	70.25	2.25
2009-10	78.13	3.66
2010-11	92.72	2.64
2011-12	102.34	13.50
2012-13	106.59	16.26
2013-14 (P)	108.76	11.95

Source: State Tourism Department. P-Provisional

Vision Tamilnadu 2023 (Phase-II)

The Vision Tamil Nadu-2023 Strategic Plan for Infrastructure Development in Tamil Nadu was launched during March 2012. The second volume of the Vision Document was released during February 2013. The investment target set for the tourism sector is Rs.10,300 crores, for development of various tourist facilities viz. Amusement Park, Under Water Ocean Park, Water Sports Complex, Special Tourism Zone, Rural Tourism Hub, Cultural Tourism Hub, Science Museum, World Class Tourism and Hospitality Training Institute, Development of Heritage Locations and Destinations of Tourist interest. It is also targeted to receive 150 lakh foreign tourists by 2023.

CONCLUSION

In the modern global village era, it is time to throw open the windows and let fresh thoughts in from all quarters. "Every place on this earth is one's own and every person is a relative" is the thought from ancient Tamil times. This is the spirit with which Tamil Nadu promotes tourism. This is the nature of the Tamils. Therefore, Tamil Nadu has come first in India in domestic tourist arrivals in 2013 for the first time and is a close second in foreign tourist arrivals. Hence, Tamilnadu can strive to make it first in both segments.

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